

Understanding dynamic emotions toward geographic environments with the integration of EEG into GIS

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1 Introduction

Conventional GIS in favor of objectivity and rationality has focused mainly on locations in the physical environment while falling short of dealing with mental space and human perceptions, feelings, and emotions [2]. Emotional factors are minimized in the majority of GIS algorithms as such factors are viewed as obstructive to spatial analysis. Nevertheless, the popularization of GIS being utilized in individuals' everyday lives and the recent trend of personalized GIS necessitate the consideration of human emotions in GIS analyses and applications. Research on urban subjective experiences and emotions with portable sensors has been an emerging field in GIS. Previous research often focuses on broad, binary natural-built urban environments that trigger emotions. How the qualities of micro-spatial factors influence emotional experiences remains unknown. Methodologically, the approaches used to study emotion vary significantly, ranging from in-depth interviews, surveys, physiological sensing, to data-intensive analyses. However, self-report measures are prone to biases due to participants' memory load and a time lag between the experience and report. Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods that learn sentiments indirectly from text or photos are subject to language, racial, and gender biases. Advances in research design and methods are imperative to carry the study a step further.

For my dissertation, I propose using a new methodological framework built on neural sensing to probe into individuals' dynamic emotions toward geographic environments. Electroencephalography (EEG), a technique that records brainwaves in a high temporal resolution, is integrated into GIS methods to learn those emotions. While mobile EEG has been advocated as a tool to study urban behaviors [5], it has never received substantial attention. As a type of embodied GIS [12], mobile EEG is untied with its users to perceive and feel geographic environments. It unveils the continuous neural processes that enable spatial cognition and emotion.

2 Theoretical framework

2.1 Emotion in GIS research

Emotion is a multifaceted experience, being physiologically, psychologically, socially, and culturally related. For example, emotion has its physiological basis. Both discrete emotions and emotion dimensions feature automatic physiological responses to sensory information. An increase or decrease in heart rate, sweating, and cutaneous blood flow, for example, can accompany various emotions. [7] applied sweat-induced electrodermal activities to indicate the emotional arousal of tourists and cyclists in the urban environment.

Emotions are conscious feelings with behavioral expressions. They reflect personal experiences and are situated in specific social, spatial, and temporal contexts. Self-report is a common approach to learning subjective emotions. Through in-depth interviews or questionnaires, participants explain their activity spaces and sense of safety, recall the stories

of their land and people that triggered emotions, rate their emotions for different trips, and/or label their emotions at various locations on a map [11]. To capture immediate emotional experiences in space, smartphone applications have been designed to pop up time-triggered or location-triggered surveys [10].

Text and photos shared on social media also carry the emotions people express. By analyzing text data through sentiment analysis, emotions can be identified as sentiment polarities such as positive, negative, and neutral feelings in relation to urban green spaces [9], and embody in residents' thoughts and judgments of their neighborhoods [3]. As facial configurations express basic emotions, emotions such as happiness were inferred from facial activities and muscle features in photos with space-time tags by using AI methods [4].

2.2 Neural sensing

The complexity and diversity of emotion and limitations of methods in previous GIS research prompt a need for methodological innovation to study human emotional responses to place. Neural sensing [2], a novel GIS approach, will be utilized in my dissertation to advance the study of emotion and place in GIS. Neural sensing involves quantifying human subjective responses to a place or the surrounding geographic environments. Emotion is one of the different subjective responses. It will be inferred from human brainwaves recorded by an EEG headset, and then be georeferenced to space. Neural sensing can also be used with interviews and questionnaires to collect personal accounts of subjective emotional experiences. It values individuals' unique experiences of places and the socio-spatial contexts in which emotions occur. Neural sensing explores the neurophysiological, psychological, and social facets of emotions toward geographic environments.

Neural sensing is analogous to the well-established practice of remote sensing and social sensing. It resonates with biosensing that uses physiological measures (mostly from the peripheral nervous system) to reveal humans' subconscious reactions to environmental stimuli [8], and portable sensing that applies mobile devices to study human behaviors and urban environments [1]. The latest progress in brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) and affective neuroscience on detecting human emotional states sheds light on the methodological framework of neural sensing. EEG is the main physiological sensor in neural sensing at its current development stage. As a non-invasive technique, a mobile and portable EEG headset has electrodes placed on a participant's scalp and records brainwaves at a high temporal resolution.

A typical equipment set of neural sensing includes a mobile EEG headset, a GPS-enabled mobile phone, and a chest-mounted camera. The EEG headset records stimulated brainwaves, which are electrical signals produced by large groups of cortical neurons in response to stimuli. EEG brainwaves consist of multiple frequency bands: delta (0-4 Hz), theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-13 Hz), beta (13-30 Hz), and gamma (30+ Hz). Each frequency band is associated with different brain states related to emotion and cognition [6]. The GPS-enabled mobile phone tracks locations at which emotions are stimulated, and allows a participant to fill out the survey. The chest-mounted camera captures the perceived environment by taking photos or videos.

3 Research questions

- RQ1: With a review of GIS research on emotion, what methodological innovation can be made to advance the examination of human emotions toward geographic environments?

- RQ2: How do individuals perceive geographic environments and what are their emotions as responses, from neurophysiology, psychology, to social meanings?
- RQ3: How can dynamic senses of place be explained by extracted factors of perceived geographic environments and participant demographics?

4 Contributions

The proposed study calls on scholarly and public attention to human emotional experiences of place – an important aspect of spatial experiences, which has been neglected by conventional GIS and is still currently understudied. The methodological framework that is built on neural sensing integrates EEG into GIS, which greatly expands the capacities of GIS to capture immediate and changing emotional responses to ambient geographic environments. It copes with the limitations of using traditional surveys solely or applying affective computing based on superficial text or facial cues without knowing users' backgrounds or contexts.

Further, the proposed study boosts a holistic understanding of our mental worlds by unveiling different facets of individuals' emplaced emotions and disproportional impacts of micro-spatial factors. It offers elicitation to synthesize human interests into GIS algorithms and applications. As such, the study results have great potential to improve the quality of urban environments and individuals' spatial experiences. It also sheds light on how personalized GIS can better serve individuals in its future development.

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